

DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

ADDITIONAL THESIS

A validation of HARMONIE cy43

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Introduction to Topic	2
1.2	Research Aim	2
1.3	Research Domain	2
2	Model	4
2.1	Model Types	4
2.1.1	HARMONIE Hindcast	4
2.1.2	HARMONIE Climatological Run	5
2.2	HARMONIE Versions	5
2.3	Experiments	6
3	Methodology	7
3.1	Data Processing	7
3.2	Statistics	7
4	Results	8
4.1	Comparison of Low Cloud Cover	9
4.2	Comparison of Cloud Fraction in the Atmosphere	12
4.2.1	Composite Diurnal Cycle of Cloud Fraction.	15
4.3	Comparison of Specific Humidity, Relative Humidity and Potential Temperature	18
4.3.1	Specific Humidity	18
4.3.2	Relative Humidity	21
4.3.3	Potential Temperature	24
4.4	Comparison of Stability of the Atmosphere	27
4.5	Comparison of cloud organization	29
4.5.1	Fish Structure	29
4.5.2	Flower Structure	31
4.5.3	Gravel Structure	32
4.5.4	Sugar Structure	34
4.5.5	Overcast	35
5	Conclusion	37
	References	38

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to Topic

It is of major importance that weather prediction models accurately describe and predict the current weather and climate. This is necessary for the day to day life, as well as to predict and determine what the future climate will be.

One of the areas of major importance when it comes to weather prediction are clouds. Clouds play an important role in radiation budget of the atmosphere. Not only due to their reflectivity but also due to their ability to absorb and re-emit long-wave radiation. Even with the current technological advancements, cloud feedbacks remain the largest source of the inter-model spread in climate sensitivity [4]. The reason for this is that the physics of clouds are still not completely understood and it becomes hard to model and predict current cloud formations.

A way to study the modelling of clouds and weather prediction in general is by using atmospheric reanalysis. Atmospheric reanalysis is a method to reconstruct the past weather by combining past observations with a dynamical model. It provides a physically and dynamically coherent description of the state of the atmosphere. The observational data is assimilated into a meteorological model with the aim to reproduce the observations as closely as possible [2].

This method of analysis will be used to validate the different weather prediction models that will be discussed in this research.

1.2 Research Aim

The main objective of this research is to validate the HIRLAM ALADIN Research on Mesoscale Operational numerical weather prediction in Euromed, hereon after referred to as HARMONIE, cycle 43 by using real life observations with the aim to determine whether HARMONIE can accurately simulate the meso-scale organization and structures of the subtropical low marine clouds.

1.3 Research Domain

The main focus of this research is clouds, specifically low marine clouds. Cloud formation depends on the relative humidity and the availability of mechanisms for lifting the air to saturation. Because the tropics have a higher relative humidity compared to other regions, it has a high consistent cloud amount throughout the whole region. A visual representation of this can be seen in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Total fractional cloud cover annual averaged from 1983-1990. Retrieved from: NASA Earth Observatory, Surface-Based and Satellite Cloud Observations. The International Satellite Cloud Climatology Project.

Clouds have the property to reflect incoming solar radiation due to their high albedo. As a result, the presence of clouds over the dark tropical oceans increases the albedo of the oceans, making tropical oceans absorb less radiation and influencing the overall radiation budget of the world. As a result, subtropical marine clouds have a substantial influence on the climate. Furthermore, shallow cumulus, such as those found in the trade-winds of the North Atlantic, can be considered the predominant cloud type on the planet [6]. Based on the points previously mentioned, it is of major importance to understand the clouds in this region.

Due to the importance of understanding and modelling low marine subtropical clouds accurately, the area of study for this evaluation is located in the tropical belt, specifically the Barbados Cloud Observatory, hereafter referred to as BCO, located on the island of Barbados ($13^{\circ}5'52''N, 59^{\circ}37'6''W$). Barbados is located in the tropics and is the most Easterly island from all of the Caribbean islands, this can be seen in figure 1.2. BCO is located on the windward coast of Barbados, and is well situated to observe undisturbed air masses carried by the trade winds over the Atlantic Ocean [6]. The site, which has been in operation since April 1, 2010, is equipped with standard meteorological instruments and several remote sensing instruments to study the vertical distribution of over-passing clouds as a function of the large-scale environment [6].

Figure 1.2: Barbados Location. Retrieved from: Google Maps.

The research period used to conduct this evaluation is from the 20th of January 2020 - 22nd of February 2020. Lastly, all of the observations obtained from the BCO will be compared to HARMONIE simulations. Results from the HARMONIE numerical weather prediction model are obtained from gridpoints, as seen in figure 1.3a. To be able to compare the observations with the simulated results, only a part of the domain of HARMONIE will be used for this research, namely gridcell 7, as shown in figure 1.3b.

(a) HARMONIE simulation domain

(b) HARMONIE gridcell 7

Figure 1.3: HARMONIE domain. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

2 Model

This research is focused on the evaluation of the HARMONIE weather prediction model cycle 43. Weather prediction models in general are computer calculations that attempt to describe the current state of the atmosphere as close as possible. These models use the laws of physics in order to calculate which weather changes are to be expected. In a weather model the atmospheric layer is divided into horizontal points (gridpoints) and vertical layers. Most models are initialised using recent data, that can be obtained from observations but also from other weather prediction models.

The Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute, in Dutch; Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI), possesses its own weather prediction model HARMONIE. This numerical weather prediction model has been in operation since 2012, and has been developed specifically for short-term weather forecasts [3]. It is a regional high-resolution meso-scale model with a non-hydrostatic dynamical core and has a resolution of 2.5x2.5 km, contains 65 levels in the vertical and has a model time step of 75 seconds [9].

An overview of the weather prediction models that will be used and discussed in this paper are presented in table 1. These will be further discussed in the following sections.

nr.	Name	Entire experiment i.d.	Cycle	Model i.d.	Model type	Description
1	EUREC4A_harm40_hindcast	BES_harm40h111_fERA5 noASSIMLL48FCINT24	40	harmonie-40h1.1.1	Hindcast	ECUME height QS = FALSE
2	EUREC4A_harm43h22tg3_hindcast		43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Hindcast	ECUME 6 height QS = TRUE
3	BES_harm43h22tg3_fERA5_exp0	BES_harm43h22tg3 fERA5_exp0	43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Climatological run	ECUME 6 height QS = TRUE
4	HA43h22tg3_clim_noHGTQS_ECUME	HA43h22tg3_clim noHGTQS_ECUME	43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Climatological run	ECUME height QS = FALSE
5	HA43h22tg3_clim_noHGTQS		43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Climatological run	ECUME 6 height QS = FALSE
6	HA43h22tg3_clim_noHGTQS_noSHAL	HA43h22tg3_clim noHGTQS_noSHAL	43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Climatological run	ECUME 6 height QS = FALSE shallow convection = FALSE
7	HA43h22tg3_clim_noSHAL	HA43h22tg3_clim noSHAL	43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Climatological run	ECUME 6 height QS = TRUE shallow convection = FALSE
8	HA43h22tg3_clim_noUVmix	HA43h22tg3_clim noUVmix	43	harmonie-43h2.2.target.3	Climatological run	ECUME 6 height QS = TRUE wind mixing = FALSE

Table 1: Overview of model cycles and type.

2.1 Model Types

The HARMONIE numerical weather prediction model can run in 2 different ways, these are hindcast and climatological runs. The difference between these runs will be discussed in the following sections.

2.1.1 HARMONIE Hindcast

In the case of the hindcast models, the model boundaries are initialised with information retrieved from the ERA-interim model run from the ECMWF. The model is run for 48 hours after initialisation. Upon 24 hours after initialisation of the run, a new run is set up using the previous 24 hour forecasted surface conditions and also run for 48 hours. This results in different sets of 48 hour runs which overlap each other every 24 hours. This process is conducted for the whole simulation period.

At the start of each simulation, the model produces some spin up issues. "Spin-up issues are a general problem for data assimilation and Numerical Weather Prediction systems. Spin-ups occur at the beginning of model runs. Due to the assimilation of observational data the model becomes slightly out of balance. Then, the model needs some time to ramp up and stabilize" [2]. For the specific hindcast models presented, it is assumed that the spin up time is less than 24 hours [10]. As a result, in order to alleviate spin-up issues, any data that was produced during the spin up process is removed. This is done by removing the first 24 hours of all 48 hour sets. Upon removing the first 24 hours of all simulation sets, the data from the whole simulation period is assimilated and the result is a continuous simulation period. It is important to note that the from the first simulation set output of 48 hours, the first 24 hours is not removed. Otherwise there would be missing data for simulation period. The complete result of this process is graphically described in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Graphical representation of initialisation for hindcast. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

2.1.2 HARMONIE Climatological Run

In contrast to the hindcast model where the model is initialised every 24 hours and ran for a total of 48 hours, the climatological runs are run for a total of 10 days without any re-initialisation, resulting in a set of 10 days with no overlapping data. One of the major consequences of this is that the resulting simulation deviates more from the observational data compared to the hindcast models. For the case of the climatological run, the lateral boundary conditions are also set using the simulation outputs of the ERA-interim model.

2.2 HARMONIE Versions

As technology advances, it is possible to do more and try different things with numerical weather prediction models. As a result of this there are different updated versions of HARMONIE, also known as different cycles. This research is mainly focused on two different cycles of the HARMONIE numerical weather prediction model, cycle 40 and 43. HARMONIE cycle 43 is an updated version of the HARMONIE cycle 40. The primary goal of the adjustments carried out on cycle 40, was to improve the underestimation of low clouds amount and overestimation of cloud base height [7].

In this section the reasons for the updates and the different changes, specifically with regards to clouds, will be briefly discussed in order to get a general view of what may affect the results. An in depth explanation of the physics and dynamics of cycle 40 and in depth information on the different updates for cycle 43 can be found in “The HARMONIE-AROME model configuration in the ALADIN-HIRLAM NWP system” [9] and “Model development in practice: A comprehensive update to the boundary layer schemes in HARMONIE-AROME cycle 40” [7] respectively.

As already described in section 2, numerical weather prediction models divide the world or region of simulation into various gridboxes, in the case of HARMONIE these have a size of 2.5x2.5km. To be able to lessen the computational power, these gridboxes are converted to *gridpoints*. This is done by taking the mean of the entire gridbox for different variables such as the temperature, humidity etc., resulting in a simulated area with different gridpoints in the middle of a gridbox, as seen in figure 2.2. A disadvantage of this is that variances within the gridbox itself are removed. This has impactful consequences for the cloud formation within the model.

Figure 2.2: Example of a gridcell and a gridpoint.

Figure 2.3 represents the sub-grid variability of the gridbox. Where q_t is the total specific humidity and q_s is the saturated specific humidity. Whenever $q_t > q_s$ clouds form, because the total specific humidity is above the maximum amount of humidity the air can hold and as a result it condenses on cloud condensation nuclei to form clouds. From this example it can be seen that due to the sub-grid variability, only in parts of the gridbox clouds are present. However, because the mean of the gridbox is taken, this variability is lost and q_t may always be lower than q_s . This may result in a simulation output that will not produce any clouds even though clouds are truly present in reality.

Figure 2.3: Variability within a gridbox.

In order to resolve this subgrid variability issue, an extra variance term with the characteristics of a relative humidity scheme was added. This has been included in the reference code since cycle 36. More in depth information on this extra variance term can be found in “Model development in practice: A comprehensive update to the boundary layer schemes in HARMONIE-AROME cycle 40” [7] .

Even with this additional variance term, cycle 40 still underestimated cloud amount. To further resolve this, an additional variance term was added on top of the already existing variance term, also referred to as height QS or LHGHT QS. This additional variance is dependent on the level layer depth. Because HARMONIE level thicknesses increase with height, the variance is low at the surface, and increases with height, reaching its maximum value at the top level. With this additional variance it was expected that HARMONIE would produce more clouds.

2.3 Experiments

Besides model runs with the default settings, there are different experimental runs where different variables can be turned off or on in order to determine their overall effect on the model dynamics. Some examples of these runs are:

- HARMONIE cy43 climate run with no additional height variance and with ECUME (nr. 4 in table 1)
- HARMONIE cy43 climate run with no additional height variance (nr. 5 in table 1)
- HARMONIE cy43 climate run with no additional height variance and no shall convection (nr. 6 in table 1)
- HARMONIE cy43 climate run with no shallow convection (nr. 7 in table 1)
- HARMONIE cy43 climate run with no U and V wind mixing (nr. 8 in table 1)

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Processing

All output data-sets from HARMONIE cycle 40 as well as cycle 43 have the dimensions:

- X Coordinate Of Projection, $x = 1269$
- Y Coordinate Of Projection, $y = 799$
- Time = 1442

In case of that the variable is height dependent an additional dimension is added which is level, level = 65.

In order to make accurate comparisons between the simulation output and the observations, the same domain must be used. As mentioned in section 1.3, the simulated domain that will be used for comparisons is gridcell 7, which is a 4x4 gridcell, just NE of BCO. In order to get only this domain from the HARMONIE simulations output, the data-set must be cut to the correct latitude and longitude.

Moreover, the HARMONIE simulation outputs are produced for the time period of 1 January 2020 up to and including 1 March 2020. As stated previously, the time domain used for the comparison will be from January 20, 2020 to February 22, 2020. Because of this the data set also has to be cut for this specific time domain.

Lastly, this 4x4 grid area must be converted to one gridpoint to be able make comparisons with point observations from the BCO. This is done by taking the mean over the grid area. Furthermore, besides the mean over the gridarea, also the mean over the entire time period is taken for HARMONIE simulations as well as the observations.

3.2 Statistics

One way to be able to determine the differences between the observed variables and the HARMONIE simulation outputs is by computing the BIAS, as described in equation 3.1. This is done by taking the sum of all differences between the expected value, in this case the simulated value, and the 'true', observed, value and dividing them by the quantity of values there are.

$$BIAS = \frac{\sum x_i - y_i}{n} \quad (3.1)$$

Where x is the model output, y is the observed values and n is the amount of values.

With the use of the BIAS it can be determined whether the model overestimates or underestimates in general. However, it is important to note that the BIAS is a mean, as a result overestimation can be cancelled out by underestimations and vice versa [1]. To avoid this problem, only the absolute BIAS will be determined, this is done as described in equation 3.2.

$$Absolute\ BIAS = x_i - y_i \quad (3.2)$$

Where x is the model output and y is the observed values. By computing this absolute BIAS, it is possible to graphically see where the model is overestimating or underestimating. And it becomes clearer which components of the model affect the simulation outputs and in what way they do this.

4 Results

To get a clear understanding of which components of the model are affecting the simulation outputs, the following comparisons will be conducted:

1. **HARMONIE hindcast cycle 40 vs. HARMONIE hindcast cycle 43.**
In order to determine the difference between cycle 40 and cycle 43 hindcast.
2. **HARMONIE hindcast cycle 43 vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 fERA5 exp0.**
In order to determine the difference between hindcast and a climatological run.
3. **HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS ECUME vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS.**
In order to determine the difference between having ECUME 6 and ECUME.
4. **HARMONIE cycle 43 fERA5 exp0 vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS**
In order to determine the difference the additional height variance makes when ECUME 6 is used.
5. **HARMONIE cycle 43 fERA5 exp0 vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 noSHAL.**
In order to determine the difference shallow convection makes when there is additional height variance present.
6. **HARMONIE cycle 43 fERA5 exp0 vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 noUVmix.**
In order to determine the difference no wind mixing makes when ECUME 6 is used and there is additional height variance present.
7. **HARMONIE cycle 43 fERA5 exp0 vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS noSHAL.**
In order to determine the effect no height variance and no shallow convection makes.

In order to make clear what the different runs are, the names presented in table 2, column 'Comparison Name', will be used ¹.

Original name	Comparison Name
HARMONIE hindcast cycle 40	HAcy40 HINDCAST
HARMONIE hindcast cycle 43	HAcy43 HINDCAST
HARMONIE cycle 43 fERA5 exp0.	HAcy43 climate run
HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS ECUME	HAcy43 climate run + no height variance + ECUME
HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS	HAcy43 climate run + no height variance
HARMONIE cycle 43 noHGTQS noSHAL	HAcy43 climate run + no height variance + no shallow convection
HARMONIE cycle 43 noSHAL	HAcy43 climate run + no shallow convection
HARMONIE cycle 43 noUVmix	HAcy43 climate run + no wind mixing

Table 2: Model run names for comparison.

All of the presented simulation runs will be compared to actual observations from the BCO. Furthermore, note that if not specifically stated in the comparisons, all simulation outputs are averaged over the period of January 20, 2020 to February 22, 2020. Moreover, all time variables are in UTC time.

¹Note that when ECUME is NOT mentioned in the model run name, ECUME 6 is being used for this run.

4.1 Comparison of Low Cloud Cover

In this section the diurnal cycle of the low cloud cover will be discussed. The overall cloud cover is the percentage of the surface on earth that is covered with clouds. To determine whether HARMONIE correctly simulates the total amount of cloud cover, all of the simulation outputs will be compared to observed cloud amount under 2500 km.

Figure 4.1: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

Figure 4.2: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

Figure 4.3: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no height variance vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

Figure 4.4: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 with no additional height variance.

Figure 4.5: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 with no shallow convection.

Figure 4.6: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 with no UV wind mixing.

Figure 4.7: Diurnal cycle of low cloud cover for HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. with HARMONIE cycle 43 with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

Name	Mean Low Cloud Cover
Observations	0.34
HAcY40 HINDCAST	0.40
HAcY43 HINDCAST	0.57
HAcY43 climate run	0.58
HAcY43 climate run + no height variance	0.33
HAcY43 climate run + no height variance + ECUME	0.32
HAcY43 climate run + no height variance + no shallow convection	0.30
HAcY43 climate run + no shallow convection	0.43
HAcY43 climate run + no wind mixing	0.53

Table 3: Mean Low Cloud Cover.

First of all, from figures 4.1, 4.2 and table 3, it can be observed that both HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast and climate run, which contain the additional height variance, have a consistent high cloud cover amount compared to HARMONIE cycle 40 runs and HARMONIE cycle 43 where no additional height variance is used. These runs have a low cloud cover mean of approximately 0.57 and 0.58 respectively. As discussed in section 2.2, this is an expected result, as the additional height variance was added to resolve the problem of underestimation of clouds by HARMONIE cycle 40. Even though the additional height variance did produce more cloud amount, it did not produce the *correct* cloud cover amount. It is overestimating the cloud amount throughout the whole diurnal cycle. Resulting in all runs containing the additional height variance to also overestimate the cloud cover amount.

From figure 4.2, it can be observed that even though one run is hindcast and the other is a climate run, there is not much difference in the simulated diurnal cloud cover amount. Both runs differ significantly, about approximately 15%, from the observed low cloud cover. As mentioned in section 2.1, it is usually expected that hindcast runs are better at simulating the observations due to the re-initialization of the model. However, in the case of HARMONIE cycle 43, it can be seen that the hindcast also deviates significantly from the observed values. This can be attributed to the additional height variance added within HARMONIE cycle 43, which makes the model produce a consistent high cloud cover amount.

Lastly, from figure 4.3 it can be seen that when there is no additional height variance present, ECUME and ECUME 6 do not make a significant difference. Both runs have a mean low cloud cover of 0.32 and 0.33 respectively. Furthermore, it can also be seen from figure 4.6, that UV wind mixing also does not have much influence on the low cloud cover output of HARMONIE, whereas shallow convection does have significant impact on the amount of cloud cover as can be seen in figure 4.5. It can be seen that HARMONIE cycle 43 climate run + no shallow convection still overestimates the cloud cover amount, due to the presence of the additional height variance. When the additional height variance is also removed, figure 4.7, the simulated diurnal cycle of the low cloud cover amount is significantly improved and resembles the observations more accurately.

4.2 Comparison of Cloud Fraction in the Atmosphere

In this section the vertical profile of the cloud fraction will be analyzed. Cloud fraction, from here on after referred to as CF, is the percentage of an area that is covered by clouds at a specific height. It is comparable to the cloud cover, but varies from the cloud cover based on the fact that it is height dependent, whereas cloud cover is measured at one specific surface or height. By measuring the CF in the atmosphere, overlapping clouds, that would not have been detected by the CC can be detected. This way it is possible to get a better and more complete view of the cloud amount in the atmosphere.

The type of clouds being studied in this research typically have tops near 2-3 km, therefore the analysis is restricted to 5000m [10]. Furthermore, besides the simulated output of the CF, also the absolute BIAS of the CF are graphically presented.

Figure 4.8: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

Figure 4.9: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.10: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and with ECUME.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.11: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.12: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 with no shallow convection.

Figure 4.13: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no UV wind mixing.

Figure 4.14: Cloud fraction HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

First of all, from all figures it can be seen that HARMONIE cycle 43 is unable to produce the clouds above 3000m. From this height upward the CF from all simulation outputs is approximately 0. Moreover, every run containing the additional height variance has the tendency to overestimate CF in the lower layers, to be specific between 1000m and 2000m. However, even these runs encounter an underestimation of the CF higher up in the atmosphere. The runs without the additional height variance, mostly underestimate the CF not only in this specific area, but also throughout the whole entirety of the atmosphere.

Based on figure 4.14a, it can be seen that when the additional variance is removed and there is no shallow convection, the simulation output somewhat resembles the observed CF near the surface, up to 2000m. However, there is still underestimation of the CF throughout the whole atmosphere.

4.2.1 Composite Diurnal Cycle of Cloud Fraction.

To get an even better view of the simulated CF in the atmosphere, some contour plots of the CF are presented.

Figure 4.15: Observed contour plot of the diurnal cycle of the cloud fraction.

Figure 4.16: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

Figure 4.17: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

Figure 4.18: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

Figure 4.19: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

Figure 4.20: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

Figure 4.21: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

Figure 4.22: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no wind mixing from U and V wind direction.

Figure 4.23: Contour plot of the mean Diurnal Cycle HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

From all of the figures presented above, it can be seen that the clouds present above approximately 3000 m, are not produced by none of the simulations. Only HARMONIE cycle 43 climate run + no height variance, figure 4.19a, is able to produce some higher clouds around time 7.00. This is a similar result as the one presented in section 4.2. Moreover, it can also be seen that the HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun, presented in figure 4.18b, has a higher overestimation of clouds compared to the other simulation outputs. This is also coinciding with the results presented in the previous section.

4.3 Comparison of Specific Humidity, Relative Humidity and Potential Temperature

To determine the reason for the over- or underestimation of clouds from the various simulation outputs, the factors influencing the cloud formation must also be analyzed. In this section the Specific humidity (q_v), Relative Humidity (RH) and the Potential Temperature (θ) from the different simulations are presented and discussed.

4.3.1 Specific Humidity

Figure 4.24: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

Figure 4.25: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.26: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.27: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.28: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

Figure 4.29: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no UV wind mixing.

Figure 4.30: Specific Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

All of the simulation outputs present a dry bias near the surface. This result is in accordance with the underestimation of cloud fraction in the same area, as presented in section 4.2. From figure 4.25a, it can be seen that between 800m and 1500m the HARMONIE cycle 43 climatological run and the hindcast pretty accurately simulate the observed specific humidity. This is contradicting based on the fact that both of these runs overestimate the total cloud fraction, as presented in section 4.2. This will be further analyzed by looking at the potential temperature in section 4.3.3. Furthermore, as already discussed, wind mixing from the U and V direction has little effect on the overall specific humidity. The dry bias is slightly enhanced when there is no wind mixing in the U and V direction.

Lastly, from figure 4.30a it can be seen that the dry bias is slightly diminished very near the surface with the use of no additional height variance and no shallow convection, between 0m and 500m. However, this is overturned by an increase in the dry bias between 500m and 1500. Between 1500m and 3000m the wet bias in the specific humidity is enhanced further compared to that of the HARMONIE cycle 43 climatological run. And to conclude, near the top, >3000 m, the run with no shallow convection and no additional height variance most accurately describes the observed specific humidity.

In order to determine the cause for the dry bias within the HARMONIE simulation outputs, it is relevant to analyze the boundary conditions received from the ERA-interim model, as presented in figure 4.31.

Figure 4.31: Mean bias with respect to radio profiles for IFS forecast (f_{c2} , solid line) and IFS analyses (ERA5, dashed line) from 2020-01-18 to 2020-02-15. The bias is calculated on a domain of about 300 x 300 km². The zero line is the line of the observations. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort. Image produced by: Alessandro Savazzi.

From the figure it is clear that the model output from the ERA-interim simulation also contains a dry bias. Near the surface this dry bias reaches a maximum of about 1.5 g / kg, which is also in the same order of magnitude as the HARMONIE cycle 43 simulation outputs. One cannot conclude that HARMONIE itself produces inaccurate results, based on the fact that the model is initialized with a dry bias.

4.3.2 Relative Humidity

Figure 4.32: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

Figure 4.33: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.34: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.35: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.36: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 with no shallow convection.

Figure 4.37: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no UV wind mixing.

Figure 4.38: Relative Humidity HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

Relative humidity in general is not an appreciable variable to analyze. It is a relative variable which is determined by the ratio of specific humidity to the saturated specific humidity. As a result of this relativity, there will not be much difference in the relative humidity outputs from the different model simulations.

However the following things can be said about the vertical profiles of RH. Near the surface, up to approximately 700m, all simulation runs have a dry bias. From figure 4.35a it can be seen that the additional height variance does not have much effect on the RH. Between 1000m-3500m the wet BIAS is very slightly diminished, but there still is a wet BIAS present. However, shallow convection does have an impact on the RH profile, especially near the surface. From figures 4.36a and 4.38a it can be seen that near the surface the simulated specific humidity closely resembles the observed RH. There is not much difference between the two figures, signifying that the presence of additional height variance does not have much effect on the RH, as already discussed.

Lastly, in the last meters, from 3000m up to 5000m, all of the simulation outputs seem to have a dry BIAS. From this one is inclined to assume that the underestimation of clouds in this area is due to the dryness of the model.

4.3.3 Potential Temperature

Figure 4.39: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

Figure 4.40: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

Figure 4.41: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.42: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.43: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.44: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no UV wind mixing.

Figure 4.45: Potential Temperature HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun vs. HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

First thing that can be noted from the potential temperature is that the cold BIAS from HARMONIE cycle 40, near the surface, is reduced with HARMONIE cycle 43. This can be seen in figure 4.39a. However, further up in the atmosphere, at around 1500m, both cycles have similar profiles.

Furthermore, from the figures presented above it can be seen that all simulations seem to have a cold bias, of about 1-1.5 degrees Kelvin, throughout the whole entirety of the atmosphere, up to 5000m. There is not much difference between the different types of runs, the removal of additional height variance, shallow convection and U and V wind mixing does not have much impact on the vertical profile of potential temperature, as can be seen from figures 4.42a, 4.43a and 4.44a respectively. However, from figure 4.41a, it can be seen that using ECUME instead of ECUME 6 does have an effect on the potential temperature, specifically in the lower layers. By using ECUME instead of the default ECUME 6 the cold BIAS near the surface is increased with about 0.25-0.5 degrees Kelvin. This enhancement of the cold BIAS is eliminated at about 3000m, where it can be seen that both simulations have the same vertical profile of potential temperature.

To further analyze the overestimation of clouds between 1000 - 2000m as presented in section 4.2, the potential temperature and specific humidity in this area are looked into. As already presented in section 4.3.1, between 800m and 1500m HARMONIE cycle 43 pretty accurately simulates the specific humidity however, in this same area HARMONIE cycle 43 presents a cold BIAS of about 1 degree Kelvin. The presence of the cold BIAS creates a favourable environment for cloud formation. Because the environment is cold, it can hold less water vapour and as a result rising parcels can reach saturation faster or at a lower level. This results in the phenomenon that even though the specific humidity may be correctly modelled, the presence of the cold BIAS produces inaccurate cloud amounts.

4.4 Comparison of Stability of the Atmosphere

Atmospheric stability is a method to determine in which state the atmosphere is in. It determines whether in the atmosphere parcels will have the tendency to rise, sink or stay at their location. The stability of the atmosphere is determined by computing the lapse rate of the environmental virtual potential temperature, $\frac{d\theta}{dz}$. The various states of stability can be classified as follows [5]:

$$\text{unstable} : \frac{d\theta}{dz} < 0 \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{neutral} : \frac{d\theta}{dz} = 0 \quad (4.2)$$

$$\text{stable} : \frac{d\theta}{dz} > 0 \quad (4.3)$$

The stability profiles for the different runs are presented in figures 4.46a up to 4.46h.

(a) Stability HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

(b) Stability HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(c) Stability HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(d) Stability HARMONIE climate run and no additional height variance.

(e) Stability HARMONIE cycle 43 with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

(f) Stability HARMONIE cycle 43 with no shallow convection.

Figure 4.46: Stability of all HARMONIE runs

First thing that can be noted from the stability profiles, is the unstable layer very close to the surface. A zoomed in version of the stability profile for HARMONIE cycle 43 climate run can be seen below, in figure 4.47.

Figure 4.47: Lowest 300 m of Stability.

This unstable layer is present in all of the simulation outputs. As the earth's surface absorbs short-wave radiation coming from the sun during the day, it gets heated and becomes hotter than its surrounding environment. As a result of this, parcels are able to rise, producing an unstable atmosphere. From this theory, it is expected that when the sun is not present, this unstable layer would become shallower or even converted into a stable layer. This can happen because at night, when the sun has set, the earth's surface is able to cool down. This can result in the surface becoming colder than the atmosphere above producing a stable atmosphere. However, from the figures it can be seen that there is not a drastic change in the unstable layer depth. There is only a slight increase in height at about 10.00 hours and a slight decrease at about 20.00 hours, converted to local time this becomes 6:00 am and 16:00 pm. This is in accordance with the time the sun rises and sets. The fact that the diurnal cycle is not very visible can be attributed to the fact that the analyzed domain is over water. Over oceans the diurnal cycle of stability is not as visible as above land because the temperature of oceans does not change drastically between day and night. As a result of this, ocean surfaces will always remain warmer than the atmosphere above and there will always be a shallow unstable layer present.

From figures 4.46e and 4.46f it can be seen that the stability in the lower levels differ from the rest of the simulations. In both of these simulation runs, shallow convection is not present. A zoomed in version of the stability can be seen in figures 4.48a and 4.48b.

Figure 4.48: Stability of the lowest 1000 meters for HARMONIE cycle 43 with no shallow convection.

From these figures it can be seen that the unstable layer is much deeper compared to the other simulation outputs. While the other simulation runs become stable from approximately 100m upward, the simulations without shallow convection remain mainly unstable, with slight areas of stability, up to 1000m. One would expect experiments without shallow convection to be more stable or at least neutral, based on the fact that shallow air parcels would not be able to rise. However, the opposite is happening. One way to explain this phenomenon is that when shallow convection is present, parcels are able to rise. As a result of this, entrainment of warm air from the top can make the profile slightly stable, this stability region is present in all figures where shallow convection is present. When shallow convection is not present, there will be less entrainment of warm air from above, making the atmosphere less warm and dry, hereby creating a deeper unstable environment above the surface.

4.5 Comparison of cloud organization

One of the most important properties of HARMONIE is the ability to reproduce the various meso-scale cloud structures that exist.

A first attempt has been made to categorize the different cloud structures [8]. These are:

- Fish structure
- Flower structure
- Gravel structure
- Sugar structure

The following section will analyze the cloud structures produced by HARMONIE and compare them with satellite observations, with the aim to determine whether HARMONIE can accurately reproduce the same organization of clouds.

4.5.1 Fish Structure

To get an overview of the fish structure produced by HARMONIE day 2020-01-22 at time 14:00 is used.

Figure 4.49: Terra satellite cloud cover overview at 14:14. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

(a) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

(b) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(c) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun

(d) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(e) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climate run with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(f) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

(g) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

(h) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no UV wind mixing.

Figure 4.50: Fish cloud structures.

Fish structures are meso-scale fishbone like clouds, that are separated from each other [8]. When the observed cloud cover is compared to the simulated cloud cover, it can be seen that both hindcast runs and the climate run are unable to produce the fish cloud structures. All three of these produce a somewhat overcast area. When it comes to the other runs, they are better at producing longer separate clouds, but are still unable to completely

produce the fish structure. It can be seen that when no shallow convection is present, the model is better at producing separate clouds.

4.5.2 Flower Structure

To get an overview of the flower structure produced by HARMONIE day 2020-02-02 at time 14:00 is used.

Figure 4.51: Terra satellite cloud cover overview at 13:56. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

(a) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

(b) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(c) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(d) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climate run with no additional height variance.

(e) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(f) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

(g) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

(h) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no U and V wind mixing.

Figure 4.52: Flower cloud structures.

Flower structures are irregularly shaped stratiform clouds, that usually appear in bunches and have a high reflective core [8]. From the figures presented above the flower structure can be recognized in all simulation outputs, based on the clouds that appear in bunches. However all simulation outputs seem to overestimate the cloud cover over the entire area.

4.5.3 Gravel Structure

To get an overview of the gravel structure produced by HARMONIE day 2020-02-05 at time 14:00 is used.

Figure 4.53: Terra satellite cloud cover overview at 14:26. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

(a) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

(b) Cloud Cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(c) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(d) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(e) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(f) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

(g) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

(h) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no U and V wind mixing.

Figure 4.54: Gravel cloud structures.

Gravel structures are cloud fields along lines or arcs [8]. From the figure presented above the gravel structure can be seen in figures, however when there is no U and V wind mixing the clouds start to accumulate and form larger clusters. This can be seen in figure 4.54h.

4.5.4 Sugar Structure

To get an overview of the fish structure produced by HARMONIE day 2020-02-11 at time 17:00 is used.

Figure 4.55: Terra satellite cloud cover overview at 16:53. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

(a) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

(b) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(c) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(d) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(e) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME.

(f) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and no shallow convection.

(g) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

(h) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no U and V wind mixing.

Figure 4.56: Sugar cloud structures.

Sugar cloud structures are very fine scale clouds which have a small vertical extension [8]. From the figures it can be seen that 4.56f and 4.56g are the best at producing the sugar structure. Both of these runs are able to produce fine clouds with a vertical extension with no sign of organization. Moreover it can be seen that HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast, climaterun and climate run without U and V wind mixing are the worst at producing the sugar structure. These runs have the tendency to produce a large area of fine clouds.

4.5.5 Overcast

To get an overview of an overcast day produced by HARMONIE day 2020-02-15 at time 15:00 is used.

Figure 4.57: Terra satellite cloud cover overview at 15:03. Retrieved from: Evaluation of the representation of subtropical marine clouds in the numerical weather prediction model HARMONIE, by F. van der Voort.

(a) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 40 hindcast.

(b) Cloud cover HARMONIE cycle 43 hindcast.

(c) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun.

(d) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance.

(e) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and using ECUME

(f) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no additional height variance and with no shallow convection.

(g) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no shallow convection.

(h) Cloud cover overview HARMONIE cycle 43 climaterun with no U and V wind mixing.

Figure 4.58: Overcast days

Lastly, when it comes to overcast days, all of the simulations seem to produce clouds overall.

5 Conclusion

HARMONIE cycle 40 was updated in order to resolve the problem of underestimation of cloud amount. This was done by adding an additional height dependent variance term, LHGTQS, to the newest cycle, HARMONIE cycle 43. From the results presented in this paper it can be concluded that the addition of the extra height dependent variance did increase the amount of cloud produced by HARMONIE. However, with this additional variance the HARMONIE model overestimated the total cloud amount, producing a mean cloud cover of approximately 0.58 compared to the true value of approximately 0.34. When the additional height variance is removed from the simulation run, the mean cloud cover is significantly reduced to about 0.32.

Furthermore it can be seen that shallow convection and wind mixing alone do not have much influence on the simulation outputs. The mean low cloud cover is reduced from 0.58 to 0.43 and 0.53 respectively. However, when it comes to low cloud cover amount, having no shallow convection along with no additional height variance does significantly improve the modelled cloud cover. The mean low cloud cover is reduced from 0.58 to 0.30.

When analyzing the vertical profile of cloud fraction in the atmosphere it can be seen that above 3000m none of the simulations are able to produce any clouds. This can be attributed to the mainly dry bias in the top, that can be observed from the specific humidity profiles. Besides this there is also a dry bias near the surface. It is likely that these dry biases are due to the cold bias from the ERA-interim simulation output. The HARMONIE simulation is initialized using these outputs, as a result the whole HARMONIE model is initialized with data already containing a dry bias.

The same can be said for the temperature. All of the HARMONIE simulation outputs have a cold bias of approximately 1 degree throughout the whole entirety of the atmosphere. A probable cause for this can also be attributed to the ERA-interim simulation outputs. It is observed that the ERA-interim produces a cold bias of approximately 0.75 K, which is comparable with the cold bias produced by the HARMONIE simulation outputs.

Moreover, it is visible that the stability of the various runs are pretty similar to each other. Every run has a very shallow layer of instability near the surface. For most of the runs this instability turns into stability moving higher into the atmosphere. For the runs without shallow convection it is noticeable that the instability is much deeper compared to the other runs. This can be attributed to the entrainment that is less compared to the other simulation outputs.

To conclude it can be said that the addition of the additional height variance within HARMONIE cycle 43 did produce more clouds, as was expected. However it still did not produce the correct cloud amounts. HARMONIE cycle 43 is still unable to accurately reproduce the meso-scale marine clouds. However, it can be seen that with the removal of the additional height variance in combination with the removal of shallow convection the low cloud cover is significantly improved, and resembles the observations pretty closely. Based on this result, it is important to further study what the impacts of having no additional height variance and no shallow convection are.

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